

D8.4 - Seminars, workshop and events - Event Nr 1

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Acronyms and definitions

Acronym	Meaning
USAL	Universidad de Salamanca
FBA	FundingBox Accelerator
B2B	Business to Business
IoT-DIH	IoT Digital Innovation Hub
NODDO	Network of Technology Centres of Castilla y León
DIGIS3	Smart, Sustainable and coheSive Digitalization conceived as a Digital Innovation Hub

Executive Summary

Deliverable D8.4, titled "Seminars, Workshops, and Events," is a key component of the dAIEDGE project, funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program. This deliverable results from Task T8.3, which focuses on the dissemination and outreach efforts within the project's Network of Excellence. The document states the agenda of the session and provides a summary of the webinar "Innovations in Edge AI: Green Blockchain, Cybersecurity, and Collaborative AI," which took place online on August 26th, 2024.

The document is structured as follows:

Introduction: Provides background and purpose.

- **Event Details:**
 - **Communication Strategy:** Describes the promotion efforts via social media, website, newsletters, and partner collaborations.
 - **Agenda:** Lists the webinar's schedule, including keynotes and panel discussions.
- **Event Summary:** Reports on participant numbers, key presentations, and outcomes.
- **Future Steps:** Details of upcoming events.

Key details from the event include the focus on cutting-edge topics such as green blockchain technology, cybersecurity challenges in edge AI environments, and the role of federated learning in collaborative AI.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Background and rationale

This deliverable D8.4 (Innovations in Edge AI: Green Blockchain, Cybersecurity, and Collaborative AI) is an outcome of task T8.3 (Network of Excellence dissemination and outreach) in work package WP8 (Communication, Dissemination, Stakeholders Engagement, Outreach and Open Calls).

This document summarizes the expert webinar held on August 26th, 2024, which was conducted online and organized by dAIEDGE. The webinar was structured into two main sections. The first section introduced the dAIEDGE project, starting with an overview of its objectives. Following this, detailed information was provided about the project's primary initiatives, including the upcoming Open Call (OC). This part of the webinar offered the academic community a chance to learn more about the first Open Call and the specifics of the exchange program. Additionally, a dedicated Q&A slot was provided specifically for the Open Call, giving interested attendees a space to ask their questions and gain further insights.

The second section of the webinar had a technical focus, inspired by the technologies used in dAIEDGE as well as other innovative technologies. This section was designed with an open approach, exploring these technologies not only within the scope of the dAIEDGE project but also discussing the latest innovations with experts both from the project and external to it. The panel discussion at the end of the webinar provided a platform for experts to address topics such as green blockchain, Federated Learning, Edge Computing, collaborative AI, and cybersecurity.

Figure 1: dAIEDGE YouTube Channel Landing Page

Hosting the webinar online was a strategic choice to reach a larger audience. Streaming it live on [the dAIEDGE YouTube channel¹](https://www.youtube.com/@daiedge) not only allowed more people to participate but also helped promote our channel. The goal was to raise awareness of the dAIEDGE YouTube channel, setting the stage for more visual content and increased public engagement in the future.

¹ <https://www.youtube.com/@daiedge>

2. Innovations in Edge AI: Green Blockchain, Cybersecurity, and Collaborative AI

2.1. D&C Strategy

Communication and Dissemination Strategy for the dAIEDGE Webinar on Innovations in Edge AI To maximize the reach and ensure the success of the webinar, we implemented the following communication and dissemination actions:

1. dAIEDGE Communication Channels

Social Media

The webinar was widely promoted through dAIEDGE's official social media channels.

Figure 2: Publication on Social Media

Figure 3: Publication on Social Media

Website

The event was featured in the "Upcoming Events" section on the dAIEDGE website, where the agenda was detailed, and registration was made available.

Figure 4: Publication on the project website

Newsletter

The webinar was announced in the quarterly dAIEDGE newsletter, reaching all subscribers and stakeholders.

Upcoming Events and Activities

**Innovations in Edge AI:
Green Blockchain,
Cybersecurity, and
Collaborative AI**

26 August 2024 (9:00 - 12:40)

We invite you to participate in our next webinar on artificial intelligence, innovation, cybersecurity, green blockchain and many more topics.

The event will feature renowned experts. **We look forward to seeing you there!**

[Register now here](#)

**European Conference on EDGE
AI Technologies and
Applications - EEAI**

dAIEDGE will be co-organiser of the next European Conference on AI EDGE Technologies and Applications, EEAI 2024.

21 - 23 October at the Hotel Regina Margherita

[Register now here](#)

Figure 5: Publication in the project newsletter

2. Collaboration with Partner Institutions

AIR Institute and USAL (BISITE Research Group). Given that we invited experts from these institutions, the event was also promoted on their respective social media platforms.

Figure 6: Social media post from a partner

Figure 7: Social media post from a partner

e4you Platform

We utilized the e4you educational platform, a project by the BISITE Research Group, Fundación General de la Universidad de Salamanca, Universidad de Salamanca, and IoT Digital Innovation Hub, which offers an open education platform.

Figure 8: Social media post from a partner

The webinar was not only listed on e4you, but apart from the information about the webinar, its program, and timing, we also disseminated details about the dAIEDGE project. Additionally, we published an interview with Alain Pagani, the coordinator of the dAIEDGE project, where he discussed the project's objectives and goals.

Figure 9: Structure of the e4you platform

Figure 10: Structure of the e4you platform

The webinar was also featured in the e4you newsletter, further enhancing its visibility.

e4you.org **campus.e4you.org**

IoT DIGITAL INNOVATION HUB | GRUPO DE INVESTIGACIÓN BISITE | UNIVERSIDAD DE SALAMANCA

e4YOU Hoy

Noticias del Campus e4YOU

¡Nueva edición de C1b3rWall Academy!

Fundamentos de Inteligencia Artificial en Ciberseguridad

Vuelve la mejor formación online en ciberseguridad de la mano de la Policía Nacional y la Universidad de Salamanca, esta vez con una edición especial gratuita basada en los fundamentos de la IA aplicable a la seguridad.

[Inscríbete](#) ¡Nuevo!

Innovations in Edge AI: Green Blockchain, Cybersecurity and Collaborative AI

¡No pierdas la oportunidad y únete al próximo **webinar** de dAIEDGE! Expertos internacionales compartirán sus conocimientos sobre ciberseguridad, green blockchain, IA colaborativa, y mucho más.

[Inscríbete](#) ¡Nuevo!

Figure 11: Publication in e4you newsletter

Other Partners

Partners such as FBA also reposted the webinar announcement on their social media platforms, further amplifying the reach and visibility of the event.

3. Additional Outreach

In addition to the above, we utilized the dAIEDGE Network of Excellence (NoE) distribution list to reach out to a broader audience within the network, leveraging its established communication channels.

2.2. Agenda

On August 26th, 2024, IoT-DIH organized an online webinar titled *"Innovations in Edge AI: Green Blockchain, Cybersecurity, and Collaborative AI."* The event was structured to provide a presentation of the project and discussions on key aspects on greenblockchain and cybersecurity. The schedule is as follows:

- 09:00 - 09:15 Opening
- 09:15 - 09:25 Brief Presentation of dAIEDGE
- 09:25 - 09:55 Presentation on Open Call
- 09:55 - 10:15 Q&A Open Call Session
- 10:15 - 10:25 Coffee Break
- 10:25 - 10:55 Keynote Address 1: Green Blockchain
- 10:55 - 11:25 Keynote Address 2: Cybersecurity within dAIEDGE
- 11:25 - 11:55 Keynote Address 3: Federated Learning and Edge Computing: Towards a Collaborative AI
- 11:55 - 12:35 Panel Discussion. Securing the Future: Innovations in Edge AI, Ciersecurity, and Green Blockchain
- 12:35 - 12:40 Closing Session & Future Prospect

**Innovations in Edge AI:
Green Blockchain, Cybersecurity,
and Collaborative AI**

26 August 2024 9:00 - 12:40 ONLINE

09:00 - 09:15
Opening

09:15 - 09:25
Brief Presentation of dAIEDGE

09:25 - 09:55
Presentation on Open Call

09:55 - 10:15
Q&A Open Call Session

10:15 - 10:25
Coffee Break

10:25 - 10:55
Keynote Address 1: Green Blockchain

10:55 - 11:25
Keynote Address 2: Cybersecurity within dAIEDGE

11:25 - 11:55
Keynote Address 3: Federated Learning and Edge Computing: Towards a Collaborative AI

11:55 - 12:35
Panel Discussion: Securing the Future: Innovations in Edge AI, Cybersecurity, and Green Blockchain
Description: Explore the convergence of Edge AI, cybersecurity advancements, and sustainable blockchain technologies. Join experts as they discuss the latest trends, challenges, and transformative potentials at the forefront of digital innovation.

12:35 - 12:40
Closing Session & Future Prospects

Register now here:
daiedge.eu/innovations-ai

 dAIEDGE
 @dAIEDGE

 Funded by the European Union

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Figure 12: Brochure of the webinar

2.3. Summary of the event

For the webinar, we registered a total of 77 people. Of these, 54 registered via the project website and social media, while the other 23 registered via the e4you platform, which was also used to promote the event, resulting in 125 people showing interest in the event. During the event, we reached a maximum of 46 live attendees. In addition, the webinar generated 182 visits.

The link to the youtube live is as follows:

<https://www.youtube.com/live/PAVsylabc0w?si=qnMNubRBII3-6Rqa>

Figure 13: Statistics from the stream

The event began with opening remarks by Javier Parra. During these first minutes, Javier Parra set the tone for the event, highlighting its importance and the main objectives expected to be achieved. An overview of the agenda was presented, and participants were encouraged to make the most of the scheduled sessions.

Alain Pagani, the project coordinator gave a brief presentation on dAIEDGE. He introduced the initiative, explaining its mission, vision, and the main objectives they were working on. He also introduced dAIEDGE’s involvement in NoE and the importance of its participation. Key aspects such as the importance of edge artificial intelligence (Edge AI) and how dAIEDGE is contributing to this field were addressed.

Figure 14: Presentation of Alain Pagani

Yolanda Moreno presented a session focused on the Open Call. During this presentation, she detailed the open call process, including objectives, eligibility criteria, the application process, and important dates. Opportunities and benefits for participants were also highlighted, as well as the types of projects they sought to fund.

Figure 15: Presentation of Yolanda Moreno

Following the presentation on the Open Call, a Q&A session was dedicated where attendees could ask questions and get direct clarifications as well as have answers to the questions raised at the time of registration to the webinar by Yolanda Moreno.

This interaction allowed participants to delve into specific aspects of the call and resolve any concerns about the process as, for example, there were assistants who presented their complete backgrounds as follows:

I am interesting about this Exchange Program, I am working as a Postdoc in the research center, VICOM. My background is related to deep learning models, especially those that are to extract features from RGB captures and 3D information such as LiDAR or other divesces.

Currently, I am working on Simulation of an human robot interaction in a warehouse environment using Isaac-simulator (NVIDIA Omniverse) to generate synthetic data. Within this topic, I have started to simulate an autonomous mobile robot (AMR) and a human with several gestures to control it. Eventually, I will work on models to identify people and gestures by an AMR and also, creating a new scenario that both of them, AMR and human, are cooperating in a task such as holding a table.

Do you think my background and/or my current expertise can be useful for some of the hosting institutions?

There were also other kinds of questions more related to the registration process such as:

Figure 16: Questions in the stream

Miguel Gómez Rodríguez delivered the first keynote address of the day, focused on "Green Blockchain." During his presentation he explored how blockchain technology can be used sustainably and ecologically. Innovations in the field, implementation examples, and the positive impact these technologies can have on the environment were discussed.

Figure 17: Presentation of Miguel Gómez

The second keynote address was presented by Manuel López Pérez, who discussed cybersecurity in the context of dAIEDGE. During these minutes, current challenges in cybersecurity, strategies for protecting data and systems in Edge AI environments, and the innovative solutions dAIEDGE is developing to address these challenges were discussed.

Figure 18: Presentation of Manuel López

Yeray Mezquita presented the third keynote address, focusing on federated learning and edge computing. During his presentation, he explained how these technologies enable collaboration in artificial intelligence without compromising data privacy. Use cases, benefits, and the future of collaborative AI in distributed environments were explored. He also answered to the doubts raised by the attendees.

Figure 19: Presentation of Yeray Mezquita

The panel discussion brought together experts such as Philippe Massonet, Yeray Mezquita, Miguel Gómez Rodríguez, and Raúl López Blanco to discuss Innovations in Edge AI, Cybersecurity, and Green Blockchain, also they tried to explore the convergence of Edge AI, cybersecurity advancements, and sustainable blockchain technologies. These experts discuss the latest trends, challenges, and transformative potentials at the forefront of digital innovation.

The panelists shared their perspectives, experiences, and visions for the future of these technologies. They discussed how these innovations can contribute to a safer and more sustainable future.

Figure 20: Screenshot of the Panel Discussion

The event concluded with a brief closing session, summarizing the key points discussed throughout the webinar. Thanks were offered to the speakers and attendees, prospects and next steps for dAIEDGE and the event's focus areas were presented. The importance of continuing collaboration and innovation in these fields to achieve a positive impact was emphasized.

3.Future Events & Next steps

This workshop is the first in a series of events that IOT-DIH will organize. Future events will provide a platform for discussing cutting-edge technologies related to AI on the edge, as well as a venue for academic publication and scientific progress.

dAIEDGE will participate in the Burgos Industria 4.0 2024 event² on September 24-25. This key event will feature two main activities:

1. **EDIH Network Session:** DIGIS3 will host a session focused on the European Network of Digital Innovation Hubs (EDIHs). This session, titled "EDIH Network Session on Industrial Track 4.0 2024 Technical Conference," will facilitate knowledge sharing and discussion on the impact of EDIH services.
2. **Industry 4.0 Matchmaking:** Following last year's success, NODDO will organize a B2B matchmaking event to connect businesses and key players in Industry 4.0. This networking opportunity will help participants (as dAIEDGE) form new partnerships and explore business prospects.

² <https://daiedge.eu/events/daiedge-will-participate-technological-meeting-burgos-industry-40-2024>

The primary objectives for IoT-DIH's participation, as part of dAIEDGE, are to:

- Build connections with stakeholders to establish the European AI Lighthouse.
- Promote the three Open Calls (OCs) and disseminate information.

daiedge.eu